

Damodar is more salt tolerant than Jaya and regulated Na⁺ and K⁺ better. For example, at pH 9.8, Damodar had maximum increase of Na⁺ (1600%) in the 4th lamina as compared to Jaya's 1178% over the respective controls.

K⁺ content of each Damodar lamina decreased less than in Jaya. Reduction in the first lamina over the respective controls was 43% for Damodar and 51% for Jaya. Thus, each part of Damodar had lower Na⁺ to K⁺ ratio than that of Jaya.

Analysis 60 d after transplanting showed that each leaf sheath had higher Na⁺ content than its lamina in both genotypes (see table). The same was true for K⁺ for the first and second leaf

Effect of sodicity on Na⁺ content of first to fourth laminae (1 L to 4 L) and their sheaths (1 LS to 4 LS) in two rices (% dry weight), Haryana, India.

pH, ESP	Variety	Na ⁺ content									
		1 L	2 L	3 L	4 L	Mean	1 LS	2 LS	3 LS	4 LS	Mean
8.2	Damodar	0.087	0.070	0.077	0.077	0.078	0.413	0.427	0.473	0.463	0.444
	Jaya	0.093	0.126	0.123	0.143	0.121	0.303	0.410	0.677	0.917	0.577
9.5	Damodar	0.650	0.760	0.903	1.10	0.854	1.21	1.53	1.86	2.12	1.68
	Jaya	0.660	0.737	0.977	1.09	0.867	1.45	1.74	1.92	2.37	1.87
Mean		0.373	0.424	0.520	0.605		0.846	1.029	1.232	1.470	
CD at 5%		S × V × L 0.023					S × V × LS 0.045				

sheaths at pH 8.1. At pH 9.5, however, each lamina had higher K⁺ than its sheath. In both varieties, sodicity decreased K⁺ content and increased Na⁺.

Higher Na⁺ in older laminae seems to

occur because of its poor retranslocation from older to younger parts. K⁺ depletion was highest in older plant parts, suggesting that export of K⁺ from older to younger parts exceeded its import under stress. *S*

Nitrogen use efficiency in relation to seedling age and transplanting time

P.S. Gill and H. N. Shahi, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Rice Research Station (RRS), Kapurthala 144601, India

We studied N use efficiency in terms of grain yield and N recovery in relation to seedling age at transplanting at PAU RRS. The 1981 and 1982 trials were in a split-plot design with 3 transplanting dates (30 Jun, 20 Jul, 9 Aug) and 5 N levels (0, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha) as main plots and 3 seedling ages at transplanting (30, 45, and 60 d) as subplots.

PK was applied at 13-25 kg/ha at last puddling. Urea N was applied in equal splits at transplanting, tillering, and panicle initiation. N recovery (kg grain/kg of applied N) was calculated:

$$\text{N recovery} = \frac{\text{Grain yield (kg/ha) in N plots} - \text{Grain yield (kg/ha) in 0 N control}}{\text{N level (kg/ha)}}$$

Transplanting 60-d-old seedlings gave highest grain yield (see figure). The differences in grain yield were most significant at later planting dates. Sixty-day-old seedlings outyielded 30 and 45-d-old seedlings with much higher differences under 0 N as well as under all other N levels with a margin of 0.58-1.1 and 0.184.48 t/ha.

Effect of transplanting schedule, N level, and seedling age on rice grain yield, Kapurthala, India.

Recovery increased with N application. Late-transplanted, 60-d seedlings had much higher N recovery than 30- and 45-d seedlings, although N recovery tended to remain at par for seedlings transplanted 30 Jun and 20 Jul.

The increase in grain yield and N recovery with older seedlings was the net result of balanced dry matter production, early flowering, and high spikelet fertility. *S*

Herbicides reduce azolla growth

J.D. Janiya, research assistant, and K. Moody, agronomist, Agronomy Department, IRRI

When azolla is inoculated in transplanted rice fields to fix N, it also competes with weeds by rapidly covering the water surface. However, it does not control all weeds. We studied